
**TRANSFORMING BRAND
ENGAGEMENT:
DAOXIANGCUN'S NEW MEDIA
ADVERTISING STRATEGY**

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of “New Media Advertising strategy of Daoxiangcun brand” is to analyse how the new media advertising strategies focused specifically on the Online platform works for a brand. The first part is concentrated on reviewing the existing literature of new media for advertising strategies. The second part of the thesis focuses on the practical part of the new media advertising, analyzing the new media campaigns on social site and their impact on a real business.

KEYWORDS: Daoxiangcun, Social Networking site advertising, Food brands, Food marketing, Advertising appeals, China.

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1. Introduction

The advance of the internet and new media has changed the conventional advertising marketing for good. New media has changed the strategies and tools for communicating with customers. It has become one of the essential factors in influencing consumer behavior. Companies have always fought for seeking consumer attention, and the advent of new media has provided a new ground for it. The high competition has forced both companies and marketers to explore new ways to reach their customers leading to the development of new media advertising. New social media has become an integral part of our lives, and it has a significant factor in influencing different aspects of our behaviors regarding purchases, opinions, evaluation, etc. Also, the ease and low cost of internet advertising marketing, as compared to the conventional ones, has enabled businesses of all kinds to reach their target audiences more efficiently. New Social media sites like Facebook, WeChat, Baidu, Twitter, Douyin, Pinterest Instagram, etc. have changed the course of internet advertising marketing. Like, the number of active daily users on just Douyin is over 600 million. This number tells us how useful Douying and other new media platforms can be for companies to promote their brand, products, and services. New media also gives its users the freedom and ability to review products and services that they use. This thing helps in influencing other potential customers and also helps the company in getting useful feedback about their product or service. It ultimately leads to improvement of products/services and better customer experience.

1.1 Background of the Study

Background of this study is to obtain knowledge and find best practices for doing new media advertising strategy of Daoxiangcun brand focusing on Douyin. The issues concerning the targeted audience, how to use the right tools, keyword selection, ad strategies and tactics, etc are also discussed. The theoretical part consists of literature review and detailed information about new media advertising. The second part will mostly deal with the practical application of the knowledge and the experience of the author. Douyin has been selected as the new media advertising platform for the thesis. The major reasons for selecting Douyin is its interesting and kind of novice concept. While there is a large amount of writing

about Douyin in the popular trade and marketing press, there has been little scholarly work so far. So, there is a need for more scholarly work and research on Douyin advertising, as it is one of the fastest growing social media with a lot of potential. This work will help many brands in planning and implementing Douyin advertising campaigns successfully. We will discuss Douyin in more detail our thesis. The idea is to use the knowledge and best practices for Douyin advertisement and find out how they can be profitable for the Daoxiangcun brand.

1.2 New Media

New media websites have rapidly become widely eminent in current society. It corresponds to a category of internet-based platforms or sites, more commonly taking the form of apps, allowing the possibility to post, share and comment on content, published by the community and organizations. In addition to that, through the exchange of information, it is important to note that New social media represents a new form of empowerment and means of information for users. Although new media is largely used by the population for this social aspect, its usage is now also incorporated by companies in their activities. Indeed, as part of the intense development of the online sector, media represents unlimited opportunities for businesses, especially regarding the selection of specific target audiences, the creation of segmented content, and the development of strong relationships with customers, i.e. creating engagement. Besides, in terms of growth, media websites are the most dynamic communication channel with an annual growth of 14%. Furthermore, even though their appearance is relatively recent, businesses found ways to make them effective in term of communication strategy, and show the extent of the possibility that they offer in comparison to traditional advertising .The fact that consumers are more connected and participative, but also that these new websites play a role in the distribution of the information, not only reinforces their dominance as an effective communication and promotional channel but also provides a considerable database, thus disturbing the field of marketing .Indeed, with Web 3.0, the value and uses of data are expanded and transformed into revenues. Also, because it expands the opportunities of the existing web services, companies need to consider the digital environment and adjust their strategy to technological advances. Advertising Marketing on new media

has to be executed differently due to the fact that users can participate, and thus create new meanings around the brand.

1.3 Networking site

The rise of new media gave birth to social networking sites. The online communities that allow people to socialize and interact with each other are known as social-networking sites. These sites allow users to connect with other users by creating personal-information profiles, inviting friends and family to gain access to those profiles, sending messages and comments, etc. The personal profiles can include various type of information about the users. It includes their names, date of birth, photos, videos, audio files and blogs. In short, social networks emerge from the ability of users to represent themselves and their interests and to network with other like-minded users. WeChat, Douyin, Facebook, Pinterest, Twitter, Instagram, VK, and Myspace are few of the best-known social networking sites. Usage of new media networks produces outcomes such as community building, content sharing and collaboration enhancement. Due to their popularity, the social-networking sites have made a significant impact on modes of social communication. The number of people using social networking sites is increasing very rapidly and at the time of writing this research more than 2.62 billion people use social-networking sites. Accepting this huge potential, many companies are using these networking sites to support their brands and increase their customer base.

WeChat-Advertising on WeChat is a booming trend: the platform has a long history of protecting users and forbidding entry from advertisers, but it is now slowly opening up. This is a huge opportunity for marketers trying to advertise in China. WeChat advertising is the Tencent program enabling companies to display promotional messages on user's timeline, in WeChat Official Account articles, or even in 3rd party Mini-programs. WeChat ads enable brands to grow WeChat Official Account followers, drive traffic to the official website or mini-program, and generate App downloads.

Douyin-Douyin, the Chinese version of Tik Tok, has taken the country by storm. With 600 million daily active users using the App an average of 67 minutes per day, Douyin is the right place to reach out to Chinese customers. Nearly half of the Chinese population uses Douyin daily (600 DAU), and is one of the Chinese social platforms with the highest user engagement and stickiness. According to Kantar and

36Kr, a user spends 120 minutes per day on average on Douyin to actively consume content and entertainment. This usage time is twice that of other social counterparts, including WeChat (61 mins), Red (57 mins), and Weibo (47 mins). Douyin users also show the highest advertising receptivity among all leading social platforms. For example, 43% of users indicate that Douyin ads are easy to accept, sometimes even entertaining to watch. A higher receptivity also leads to a better feeling for the brand and makes conversion more likely to happen.

Figure 1: Average daily time spent by users

Source: Kantar, Media Reaction 2020

This study focuses on exploring the ways food companies use Instagram posts to be perceived by consumers as brands, attached to healthy and conscious concerns. Therefore, this paper contributes to the current theories about food advertisements and Douyin marketing uses.

Pinterest- Pinterest is one of the most popular social-networking sites, especially among women and kids. It is one of the fastest growing websites in history. Within a few years of its launch, it was able to get over 11 million users. Also, the average visits to Pinterest lasts approximately 97.8 minutes, that allowed Pinterest to be ranked higher than most of the other social networking sites in terms of user engagement. Due to this high engagement rate and rapid growth, it attracted many users and brands. Pinterest is a marketing force to be reckoned with, evolving on a steady basis to help brands deliver more engaging content and reach the right customers. Few of the most important benefits, Pinterest marketing offers, are: Increased awareness, high website traffic, high user engagement, lead generation, etc.

Instagram-Instagram is a social networking site used for photo sharing from mobile devices (Scott, 2013). There were approximately more than 77.6 million active Instagram users in the United States in 2015. This number is projected to cross 111 million in 2019. It is most popular among teens and young millennials. Globally speaking, 41 percent of the users are 24 years or younger. Because of the visual nature of Instagram, it is a very valuable social media marketing tool. 98 percent of fashion brands had an Instagram profile as of March 2016 (Statista, 2019). All these numbers show that Instagram is a great tool for marketing, and it offers a wide range of benefits to companies, in terms of marketing. Some of these benefits include: better targeting of audience, as Instagram also uses the data from Facebook, Instagram ads are non-intrusive and less likely to annoy the targeted audience, Instagram has a higher engagement rate than most of the other social media platform, etc. The number of social media users has shown a rapid growth in the last few years and is projected to increase steadily. There are 3.175 billion active internet users in the world, out of which, 2.206 billion are active social media users (Statista, 2019). In 2017, 71% of the total internet users were social network users and this percentage is projected to increase. The most popular activity among internet users is social networking and it has a high user engagement rate. With social media penetration of over 66%, North America ranks first among regions where social media is most popular (Statista, 2019). More than 81% of US population had a social media profile in 2016.

Figure1: Number of New media users from 2010 to 2021

Source: (statista,2019)

Another important thing to consider, while discussing social networking sites, are the platforms on which these social networking sites are used. Mobile and smartphones have become the most popular devices for using social networking sites. The most popular purpose of smartphone app usage other than gaming is using social media to connect with other people (Jeff, 2014). A report from comScore shows that both Facebook and Twitter users spend more time using those networks on mobile devices than they do on traditional computers or laptops, also, it was noted that the apps drive the majority of engagement on mobile devices- 4 out of every 5 minutes consuming media on mobile devices are via apps. An average Facebook mobile user spends more than 7 hours per month while the 25.6 million twitter mobile users had an average engagement of nearly 2 hours per month, in comparison the people visiting twitter on their computers spent just 20.4 minutes (Forbes, 2019). As seen in the below figure, the number of mobile phone users worldwide is steadily increasing and is projected to reach 4.78 billion by 2020.

Figure2: Number of mobile phone users worldwide from 2015 to 2020

Source: Statista 2019

Facebook-Facebook is the largest social-networking site. It has over 2.32 billion monthly active users worldwide. It was initially created by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004 for the purpose of staying in touch with his fellow students at Harvard University. Facebook is a free social-networking site that allows registered users to create profiles, upload photos and videos, send messages and keep in touch with friends, family and colleagues (Spencer S., 2014). The average Facebook user spends almost one hour per day and the potential of having successful marketing campaign is immense. Facebook has developed an advertising platform that enables very accurate targeting. Depending on the personal information of the user, marketers can choose which users that will see the ad on Facebook. It can be divided by gender,

geographic area, age, interests, education, birthday, workplace, relationship status, language and connections. From a marketing perspective, Facebook offers a wide range of benefits for marketers. Few of the most prominent benefits includes; Massive exposure on global scale, Low marketing costs, sophisticated targeting tools, etc.

Twitter-Twitter is a microblogging social networking site (short messages) which encourages communication between users and their followers (Spencer S., 2014). Twitter only allows users to “tweet” messages of 140 characters or less to their contacts. The contact is known as followers. It is a unique way of communication that allows users to share ideas, news, and hyperlinks to reach a wider audience. It also helps professionals to broadcast a link to their blogs and send their tweets automatically to their other social media applications (Fischer, 2011). In terms of marketing and business, Twitter is one of the biggest marketing phenomena of the online business world. As a marketing platform, it offers many benefits to a business Few of the core benefits of marketing on twitter are: increased customer satisfaction with better customer service, more effective communication with customers, increased traffic to the company website, ability to follow trends and watch competitors closely, etc.

1.4 Douyin for Advertising

The rise of visual content sharing sites has brought many changes in the new media landscape. The importance of visual content sharing in new media can be realized from the explosive growth of the latest visual-content sharing sites such as Douyin, Instagram, Pinterest and Snapchat – especially in an industry like Daoxiangcun brand where the main focus is on aesthetics and visual representations. In the current landscape of new media, many food brands are experimenting with the power of visual content, using images and videos to build brand awareness and engaging consumers. Advertising on Douyin is one of the most effective ways to directly drive traffic from the platform. Did you know that promoted brand on verified accounts with a blue V drive 27% more traffic to the account? You can experiment with different types of ad placements on the platform. These are – open screen ads, feed ads, sticker ads and music ads.

1.5 Research Problem

New media and Advertising are central to the food industry. They explain the large mediatization of food is due to the repetitive need for the items and the competitive market. the food brand industry faces competitive pressures and the market has become highly saturated. For these reasons, brands need to differentiate themselves in the competitive landscape, reach consumers at the emotional level and show identical convictions. For food brands, the decision to focus on promoting healthy and conscious products, especially via media, is driven by several strong motivations. Moreover, to remain competitive and meet consumer demand. Advertising strategies based on healthy lifestyle represent potential keys to success in the food industry.

1.6 Research Question

The main research question is formulated as follows: “How do food companies use social site like Douyin as an advertising site to promote their brand.

The subject of the study concerns company executing business activities in order to promote the brand to consumers. Food brands mention that the purpose of their advertisements is to inform consumers about their company and their products in order to enable consumers to make conscious choices in their purchasing and consumption. media studies have shown the increasing use of the Douyin in terms of advertising and commercial value. For these reasons, I decided to focus my research on the use of this platform.

Several sub-questions helped to study the topic and served as thematic steps in order to answer the main research question.

Question 1:

What drives the selection of a specific target audience for an Douyin advertising marketing campaign of the brands?

Question 2:

What advertising appeals are being used to promote Daoxiangcun Brand on Douyin?

1.7 Academic Relevance

The impact of food brand advertising on new media on the young population .and the effects of food posts online on consumers' purchasing choices. Also, studies focused on the creation of functional foods, the implementation of quality tools such as labels and the promotion of corporate social responsibility. No studies about the way food companies use new media platforms to be perceived as healthy and conscious have been found.

2. Theoretical framework

The topic of this study is relatively recent, there have only been a small number of directly linked studies. The connection of several theoretical approaches discussions of concepts appears very insightful to investigate the ways food companies use Douyin as an advertising channel to be perceived as brands. Many researchers have explored the ways new media and especially Douyin represent valuable advertising platforms. These are especially relevant to this study as they not only help to understand the benefits of these digital social websites in terms of traffic, and brand visibility, but also in shaping users' opinions. For this reason, it seems relevant to study theories regarding consumer segmentation in that industry to better understand what leads to food brands to select a specific audience when implementing their advertising campaign. The integrating advertising in promotional messages is very beneficial for brands as they strongly influence customers' beliefs and attitudes. assert the value of implementing emotional and rational appeals in new media advertising. Both of these appeals are relevant in the promotion of food brand. since new media platforms are relevant and rich channels for the promotion and perception of lifestyle because they are part of the culture and highly influential particularly in the field of food consumption. For this reason, a combination of relevant literature on that topic will be explicitly examined in the fourth and final section of this chapter.

2.1 Advertising

Advertising is a marketing communication that employs an openly sponsored, non-personal message to promote or sell a product, service or idea.⁴⁶⁵ Sponsors of advertising are typically businesses wishing to promote their products or services. Advertising is differentiated from public relation in that an

advertiser pays for and has control over the message. It differs from personal selling in that the message is non-personal, i.e., not directed to a particular individual. Advertising is communicated through various mass media including traditional media such as newspapers, magazines, television, radio, outdoor advertising or direct mail and new media such as search results, blogs, social media, websites or text messages. The actual presentation of the message in a medium is referred to as an advertisement. Commercial advertisements often seek to generate increased consumption of their products or services through “branding”, which associates a product name or image with certain qualities in the minds of consumers. On the other hand, ads that intend to elicit an immediate sale are known as direct-response advertising. Non-commercial entities that advertise more than consumer products or services include political parties, interest groups, religious organizations and governmental agencies. Non-profit organizations may use free modes of persuasion, such as a public service announcement. Advertising may also help to reassure employees or shareholders that a company is viable or successful. Modern advertising originated with the techniques introduced with tobacco advertising in the 1920s, most significantly with the campaigns of Edward Bernays, considered the founder of modern, “Madison Avenue” advertising. Worldwide spending on advertising in 2015 amounted to an estimated US \$ 529.43 billion. Advertising's projected distribution for 2017 was 40.4% on TV, 33.3% on digital, 9% on newspapers, 6.9% on magazines, 5.8% on outdoor and 4.3% on radio Internationally.

2.2 Advertising Definition

Advertising is a means of communication with the users of a product or service. Advertisements are messages paid for by those who send them and are intended to inform or influence people who receive them, as defined by the Advertising Association of the UK.

Advertising is always present, though people may not be aware of it. In today's world, advertising uses every possible media to get its message through. It does this via television, print (newspapers, magazines, journals etc), radio, press, internet, direct selling, hoardings, mailers, contests, sponsorships, posters, clothes, events, colours, sounds, visuals and even people (endorsements).The advertising

industry is made of companies that advertise, agencies that create the advertisements, media that carries the ads, and a host of people like copy editors, visualizers, brand managers, researchers, creative heads and designers who take it the last mile to the customer or receiver. A company that needs to advertise itself and/or its products hires an advertising agency. The company briefs the agency on the brand, its imagery, the ideals and values behind it, the target segments and so on. The agencies convert the ideas and concepts to create the visuals, text, layouts and themes to communicate with the user. After approval from the client, the ads go on air, as per the bookings done by the agency's media buying unit.

2.3 Advertising process

The process of advertising is the integration of various activities and giving importance to each in a rational manner. Advertising Design process:

Advertising design involves running an integrated ad campaign to reach achieve your present business goal. Based on the objective, a reasonable budget is calculated on which the media plan is formulated. A creative concept is finalized, which is then transformed into various artworks deployed through various mediums in specific time intervals for specified time duration which will help your business reach its goal.

Figure 3: Advertising Design process

Source: Lemon7

The step Involved in the process of advertising: For the development of advertising and to get best results one need to follow the advertising process step by step:

Figure4: step involved in the process of advertising

Source Lemon7

Step1-Briefing: The advertiser needs to brief about the product or the service which has to be advertised and doing the SWOT analysis of the company and the product.

Step2-Knowing the objective: One should first know the objective or the purpose of advertising what is to be delivered to the audience.

Step3-Research: This step involves finding out of market behavior, knowing the competitors, what type of advertising they are using, what is the response of the consumers, availability of the resources needed in the process etc.

Step4- Target Audience: the next step is to identify the target consumers most likely to buy the product. The target should be appropriately identified without any confusion. For e.g. If the product is a health drink for the growing kids, the target customers will be the parents who are going to buy it and not the kids who are going to drink it.

Step5- Media Selection: Now that the target audience is identified, one should select an appropriate media for advertising so that the customers who are to be informed about the product and are willing to buy are successfully reached.

Step6-setting the budget: then the advertising budget has to be planned so that there is no short of funds or excess of funds during the process of advertising and also there are no losses to the company.

Step7-Designing and creating the Ad: first the design that is the outline of ad on papers is made by the copywriters of the agency, then the actual creation of ad is done with help of the art directors and the creative personnel of the agency.

Step8-perfection: then the created ad is reexamined and the ad is redefined to make it perfect to enter the market.

Step9-place & time of Ad: the next step is to decide where and when the ad will be shown. The place will be decided according to the target customers where the ad is most visible clearly to them. The finalization of the time on which the Ad will be telecasted or shown on the selected media will be done by the traffic department of the agency.

Step10-Execution: Finally, the advertisers released with perfect creation, perfect placement and perfect timing in the market.

Step11- performance: the last step is to judge the performance of the ad in terms of the response from the customers, whether they are satisfied with the ad and the product, did the ad reached all the targeted people, was the advertise capable enough to compete with the other players etc. every point is studied properly and changes made if any. If this step followed properly then there has to be successful begging for the product in the market.

Advertising campaign- meaning and process: Advertising campaign are the groups of advertising messages which are similar in nature. They share same message and themes placed in different types of medias at some fixed time. The time frames of advertising campaigns are fixed and specifically defined. The very prime thing before making an ad campaign is to know: 1. Why you are advertising and what are you advertising.?

Why refers to the objective of advertising campaign. The objective of an advertising campaign is to..

- Inform people about your product
- Convince them to buy the product
- Make your product available to the customers

Figure5: Advertising campaign

3. New Media

As briefly explained in the introduction chapter, new media has become a valuable and recognized advertising channel by marketers who do not hesitate to incorporate it in their strategy. New media marketing refers to a type of online marketing using social media websites as a tool. This aims to create customer awareness and product recognition, but also provides an ideal platform for content exposure. Several NMM practices seem to be useful to implement by businesses such as branding, customer relationship management, electronic word of mouth (e-WOM), and advertising. In other words, new media is not only a highly utilized platform for social interactions, but also represents a very beneficial platform for brands to communicate, and advertise their products for sales stimulation. Moreover, as discussed in the previous chapter, Instagram currently stands out in terms of user numbers and business possibilities. Therefore, it seems insightful to better understand what possibilities SM websites offer with regard to the advertising channel. This will constitute the focal point of the first subchapter. Also, a deeper understanding of the opportunities enabled by Instagram's advertising tools is appropriate for this study, so it will be the focus of the second subchapter.

3.1 New Media Advertising

New media marketing centers on promoting brands and selling products and services through established and emerging online channels, harnessing these elements of new media to engage potential

and current customers. New media marketing encompasses many different mediums, including display advertising, content marketing and social media promotions. The objective of all new media marketing is to get consumers to interact with the brand, engaging them in a way that increases awareness and correlates to sales.

The Question is “How is new media marketing changing ecommerce?”

Consumers today are empowered with an incredible amount of information, allowing them to thoroughly research their purchases before contacting a business. In fact, most people decide to buy before talking to a sales professional, Web services company Market 8 reported. This paradigm shift between buyers and sellers has forced businesses to change their approach to marketing. New media helps online businesses:

- Gather customer data: New media helps companies gather far more detail about their target customers. By using sophisticated programs like customer relationship management systems, businesses can collect information about their best customers and use it to nurture long-term relationships.
- Build relationships: Since most customers guide themselves through the sales process, companies need to establish a relationship with them before they are ready to buy. Businesses use tools like social media to interact with people on a personal level, sharing information and experiences in a way that humanizes the brand.
- Know when to sell: People are inundated with advertisements all day long. Studies have shown that the average person sees 5000 ads or more every day according to market research firm SJ Insights, resulting in a certain amount of "ad blindness" among users browsing the Internet. How can your business stand out when the entire world is clambering for attention? Sometimes the solution is to stop promoting your brand and focus instead on people and their needs. Knowing when and how often to send out a sales message is a key component to new media marketing success.

Successful new media marketing strategies: New media marketing is an ever-changing effort for businesses. Here are just a few of the areas where brands are growing online.

- Video marketing businesses: The market has discovered there is no better way to capture the attention of consumers than with video. About 65 percent of people will watch most of a video as compared to reading content, marketing enablement firm Brainshark reported. Companies can use online course and learning platform and teach consumers how to use their products and demonstrate different features while also crafting a brand personality people enjoy.

Maintaining a dynamic website: It's no longer enough to just have a presence on the Web. Brands need dynamic websites with fresh content posted often, encouraging people to return and stay engaged with your brand. Search engine optimization: Ranking on page one of search engine results is an important goal for every business. By continually updating your website with fresh, informative content and earning inbound links from quality websites, your business will see progressive gains in this important channel. By using advanced marketing analytics to link your content to specific conversion goals, you can easily quantify the impact of your efforts on the bottom line.

Social media marketing: Building relationships with people on social media depends on using good listening skills and responding to things people talk about. When people start thinking of your brand as a trusted resource, they are far more likely to do business with you.

3.2 Advantages of New Media Advertising

New media has taken the world by storm over recent years. To this end, it is essential that your business is both present and active on new media if you really want to connect with your target audience. There are approximately 4.14 billion active new social media users, according to the Digital 2020 report by Hootsuite. This is 53% of the world's population, and a massive 88.9% of the 4.66 billion internet users. With so many people using new media platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Douyin, WeChat, Pinterest, Weibo and Instagram every single day, new media advertising is a marketing strategy that you do not want to miss out on. In the China alone, a reported \$61.81 billion was spent on new media ads in 2018. With a 25% year-on-year increase in new media ad spend, it's clear that many businesses across the China value the potential power of new media advertising. There are many ways we can use new media to meet our business objectives, and one of those ways is through new media advertising.

7 advantages of new media advertising

Whether you want to target teens on Douyin (Chinese version of TikTok) make yourself known to millennials on Twitter, success lies in developing the best new media advertising strategy for your business. In order to do this, you need to understand the advantages of new media advertising, and how

these can be applied to your business. There are multiple advantages of new media advertising. If new media ads aren't already part of your wider marketing strategy, you could be missing out on the opportunity to reach more people, generate higher conversions, and nurture greater customer satisfaction levels.

1. Increased brand awareness

By promoting your business, products or services across new media, you are increasing brand awareness from the get-go. Even before clicks and conversions come into play, you are putting your brand out there to millions of people by using new media ads. Appearing in people's new media feeds with a 'sponsored' label or showing up in front of a YouTube video can do wonders for increasing your brand visibility, helping your business to stay fresh in people's minds – even if it's on a subconscious level. Increasing your brand awareness, of course, has many benefits for your business. Whether you are a newcomer within your industry or you are a well-established brand, this increased exposure from new media advertising could result in fresh leads and higher conversions for your business.

2. Improved brand loyalty

Engaging with your customers on new media can help your business develop a loyal customer base. New media advertising is about more than promoting your products or services. It offers the opportunity to connect with your target audience and develop meaningful connections. New media advertising can be a great demonstration of social proofing, which in turn, can improve brand loyalty and turn one-time visitors into lifelong customers. You can use new media advertising to share customer testimonials or case studies to demonstrate customer satisfaction.

3. Higher conversion rates

New media advertising can help your brand generate more conversions. In fact, 27% of people surveyed in the Digital 2020 report stated that they found new brands and products through new media adverts. There are several ways to boost your conversion rate with new media advertising.

4. Boost leads for your business

As you already know, new media advertising is a great way to get your brand in front of more people and expand your customer base. By running specific lead generation ad campaigns, you can really harness the benefits of new media advertising for your business.

5. Low-cost advertising

When it comes to new media advertising, your biggest concern may be “how much will this cost?”. The good news is new media advertising can be a cost-effective solution for your brand. Most new media advertising models operate on a pay-per-click (PPC) or pay-per-view (PPV) basis meaning you only pay when someone has clicked on your ad, or viewed your video ad. As a result, you can keep your advertising costs low and only pay when someone takes action.

6. User-friendly interface

Advertising on new media doesn't have to be scary. Most new media giants offer a user-friendly advertising platform. Most of these platforms will walk you through each step of setting up your advertising campaign from choosing an objective to inputting your audience requirements and specifying your budget. Then when it's time to publish your adverts, you can easily monitor the advert performance and use these insights to make informed decisions about how best to optimize your adverts for success.

7. In-depth analytics

Last but not least, another advantage of new media advertising is having access to a wealth of analytics and statistics which, we're sure you will agree, is any marketer's dream! You are able to see, almost instantly, how well your campaigns are performing and how past campaigns performed. This allows you to tailor your future campaigns to ensure they are as successful as possible, as well as optimizing live campaigns and developing A/B tests to refine your new media advertising strategy. The benefits of new media advertising analytics don't stop there. You can also use these advertising insights to improve other areas of your business. For instance, your new media adverts could give you a good indication of brand sentiment, allowing you to create organic content that you know your target customers love to see online. Using your social media advertising analytics in collaboration with Google / Baidu Analytics, you will be able to gain a deeper understanding of the marketing tactics that work best for your brand promoting.

3.3 Advertising of The Brand

Advertising refers to the creative way brands connect their products with consumers' demand in terms of needs, benefits, and desires. The advertising retrieved from promotional images or messages represents the most important aspect for the audience. When well defined, advertising establish a creative context and add more consistency within a advertising campaign. Advertising is commonly separated into two distinct groups. They refer to the performance and clear functional aspects such as quality or expertise. Second, emotional advertising, on the contrary, relate to more hedonic desires, but also audiences' underlying feelings, need for stimulation of personal expression, but also self-esteem. They tend to encourage positive feelings such as humor, joy or pride, or limit the negatives such as guilt. Literature indicates that the definition of and focus on advertising are notably relevant in the digital era as advertising marketers can easily identify their performance, for example, by measuring the engagement created around them in media.

3.3.1 Advertising appeals and new media

New media has intensively participated in the shift and involvement of new advertisement channels, the implementation of effective and successful advertising campaigns in these platforms can be challenging. Also, one way to analyze their intended impacts is to look at consumers' brand perception developed via the ads. States that the messages and signals used in new media can influence customers' perception and attitudes. Also, arguably that the language implemented by brands relate to either emotional or rational appeals. The use of emotional appeals triggers strong emotional responses and seem to generate strong motivational relevance. Furthermore, posts based on emotional appeals appear to be more likely to be shared between users. Besides, argue that the stronger the emotions that are incorporated in new media ads, the most likely users will develop a positive brand image. The term informativeness relates to the given definition of rational appeal. It corresponds to the capacity to inform the audience about the product's features to allow them to make choices corresponding to the characteristics that they value as important. In other words, the use of informative messages in ads should help customers to evaluate the features and make more rational decisions. Some are claim in

their research that the display of information in ads seem to be more valuable to more consumers. Therefore, the use of informative content in new media most likely generates a positive image about the brand, and helps spread the ad over the consumers' network. So, this idea supports the research of new media, the use of utilitarian values amplifies audiences' positive perception of a brand.

3.3.2 Advertising appeal and Bakery food product promotion

Some people are claiming the relevance of studying the emotional and rational appeals used in the promotion of food brand, explaining that these two approaches are often incorporated in the design of persuasive strategies. For the authors, in the context of food, the rational appeal also mentioned as cognitive components of attitudes involves the target's beliefs, attributes, and attitudes regarding the product. The emotional appeals, mentioned as the affective component, reflect the feelings, sensations, and experiences about the food, such as the pleasure or recall of pleasant memories. the promotion of health attributes related to food generally employs a rather informational tone and triggers rational benefits, while food marketers tend to focus on emotions such as pleasure. However, as a matter of fact, literature appears to discuss the use of these two distinct appeals when promoting food brand, including the most common emotional benefits used in food advertising. First, many studies note that food companies, in their ads, strive to trigger the emotional benefits for their targets. What is most commonly used in food advertising refers to the notion of pleasure and its strong influence on customer perception. Indeed, multiple authors in the field of food appeal and advertising have investigated the sentiments and motivation behind the temptation of food products. It appears that the emotions related to pleasure are involved not only in the consumption but also the anticipation, preparation and contemplation. Relating to the contemplation, the appearance of the items plays an essential role. confirms that idea, explaining that this looking aspect influences and motivates the emotions of pleasure and stimulates the desire of consumption. Besides, the pleasant emotions produced by food can be associated with previous joyful experiences and memories. Moreover, More argue that although the thought of food alone can result in pleasure stimulation, the presence of representative visuals can highly reinforce that emotion. Furthermore, considering the fact that individual emotional responses affect purchasing choice and

consumption concludes that developing a strong pleasure appeal is very effective in terms of food promotion.

4. Introduction of the company

4.1 Daoxiangcun Brand

Most locals in Beijing will know what you are talking about when you mention Daoxiangcun. As one of the capital's time-honored brands, Daoxiangcun snacks have found their way into the hearts, and stomachs of countless Beijingers. Daoxiangcun formerly Suzhou Daoxiangcun, is one of the oldest existing enterprises in the Chinese bakery industry, founded in 1773 in Suzhou. According to the results of the 2019 Chinese brand valuation, Daoxiangcun ranks fifth with a brand value of 13.31 billion yuan. So far, Daoxiangcun had owned Suzhou, Beijing, Shandong, Jinxiang, Henan, Daoxiangcun Science and Technology Co., Ltd, Zhangjiagang Fujijia Food Co., Ltd and Beijing Daoxiangcun Private Food Co., Ltd under its wing. In terms of distribution channels, Daoxiangcun has nearly 700 specialty stores in China, with growth reaching nearly 100 each year. In 2009, Daoxiangcun launched the 'Internet+Daoxiangcun' strategy after establishing the Electronic Commerce Department. Through this, sales of confectionery and mooncakes have been at the forefront of T-mall and Jingdong e-commerce for many years. Sales of Daoxiangcun e-commerce channels have increased year by year, already approaching 30%. In addition, the "Daoxiangcun Village Goes to Sea" strategy has been implemented. In 2006, he registered trademarks of "Daoxiangcun" in more than 30 countries and regions overseas, and exported products to more than 30 countries through cross-border door shops and the District. Daoxiangcun, there are many types of products, including cakes, leisure foods, holiday foods, nuts, bread staple foods and instant frozen foods. Among them, rice cakes made in this company have won the approval of many consumers with their unique characteristics, and are praised as the Gaodiantaidou for signature product. Nowadays, no matter for the locals or the travelers, Beijing Daoxiangcun is a must-go place. People come here to buy pastries to feed their own appetite or to take to their friends and relatives as gifts. In recent years, the pastry market has become very hot, and many Internet celebrities and national trendy dim sum brands have sprung up. In the face of fierce competition, Daoxiangcun which has a profound heritage of 249 years, has always adhered to the century-old

reputation of the time-honored brand. Through the innovation and inheritance of traditional skills, it has protected the core quality of Daoxiangcun's brand and implemented the taste and texture that consumers care about most. After a long period of persistence, Daoxiang Village has occupied the leading position in the pastry category and moon cake category for many years on e-commerce platforms such as Tmall and JD.com. Not only that, according to the "2021 China Mooncake Industry New Consumption Trend Research Report" released by iMedia Research, in 2021, consumers will choose mooncake brands in Daoxiangcun with a proportion of 49.5%.

Figure6: selected brand of Chinese moon cake consumers in 2021

It can be seen that no matter from the sales data or word-of-mouth evaluation, Daoxiangcun moon cakes have a high degree of recognition in the minds of consumers. Mention moon cakes and think of "Daoxiang Village", and mention "Daoxiang Village" which has become the consumption habit of many consumers, and the century-old quality of Daoxiang Village has not disappointed consumers. Once inside, customers have over a hundred snacks and cakes to choose from, but the one marked "Eight Treasures of Beijing" is always the hottest seller. It's bright red gift-box and attractive design makes it perfect for offering good wishes when visiting friends during festivals.

Figure7: Eight Treasures of Beijing

Source: google Image

“This is the "Eight Treasures of Beijing". It includes eight styles of cakes such as candied fritter, and jujube flower shortbread cake.

4.2 Situation Analysis

An advertising situation analysis provides an overview of a company's image in comparison with similar organizations in the marketplace. A situation analysis is usually created before an advertising campaign. This piece of research provides executives with an accurate picture of consumer' perception of both the company and its competitors. By assessing a company's strengths and weaknesses, advertisers can focus on issues and messages that will resonate strongly with their clients' target audience. It consists of several methods of analysis. This section will only discuss the four parts of the analysis that includes: company, competitors, customers, goals.

4.2.1 Business

Business needs to evaluate its objectives, strategy, capabilities and target audience. Also, the business needs to decide what products to promote and whether or not those products are suitable for online promotion. In the case of Daoxiangcun brand, the target audience is present online and also the products are suitable for online promotion. Hence the most suitable way to reach the target audience is through online promotion. Also, the site has been running for a few years and has presence on most of the major social networking platforms. This thing is helpful in reaching new potential customers and staying in touch with the current ones. The brand has been running and is generating some revenue since its launch.

An overview of the sales and orders for moon cake of Daoxiangcun brand from 2015 to 2021 has been shown in the figure below.

Figure8: Moon cake sales in China

Source: iMedia Research Graphics: GT

The figure shows the gross sale made during the period of 2015 to 2021.

4.2.2 Competitors

China's bakery industry is still dominated by local small and medium-sized baking food enterprises, with a decentralized competition pattern. China's baking food industry has a low entry threshold; small bakeries are dividing the market due to low entry barriers for the Chinese bakery industry. and the industry is fiercely competitive. At this stage, there are three types of participants in the bakery industry. First, there are local small and medium-sized baking food enterprises. This type of enterprises is small but in large numbers, accounting for more than 70% of the market share in the bakery industry. there are so many domestic chain baked goods enterprises. This type of enterprises has the following three characteristics including i) more regional links, fewer nationwide chain enterprises, ii) more products have the advantage in price due to scale production, iii) they are good at traditional channels, most of them are distributed in second, third line cities and rural markets. Here are the Some competitors of Daoxiangcun brand in China, Holiland Bakery (好利来), Guifaxiang (桂发祥), Toly Bread (桃李面包), Guangzhou Restaurant (广州酒家), Bliss Cake (幸福西饼), and MAKY (米旗).

Figure 9: competitors of Daoxiangcun brand

4.2. Costumers

Cakes and bread are the most popular baked goods in the Chinese market. In terms of gender, Chinese women are more interested in bread and cakes than men, which accounts for 65% of sales in 2017.

Figure10: Bakery food consumers rate in China (by Gender & age)

Source: soho.com

In addition, most sales in 2017 came from those who born in the post-80s and 90s. It can be inferred that bread in China and cakes in China are mainly preferred by young consumers. For them, bread is not only breakfast but also a popular choice for afternoon tea. Nowadays, baked goods in China such as bread and cake are common for Chinese people to eat as snacks or breakfast. Young consumers and aging consumers have different preferences towards baked products. What they have in common is the desire for healthy and delicious baked goods. Young consumers like baked goods with various tastes, this is one of the reasons why there are so many different flavors of baked goods in China. Besides,

product packaging is also considered by consumers. Small packages are more preferred by young consumers for they are easy to carry and suitable for office workers to replenish energy. On the other hand, aging people prefer baked goods with bigger packages since they like sharing snacks with their family or friends. Older consumers also tend to prefer soft baked goods with less sugar. So Daoxiangcun brand will focus on female & young consumers.

4.2.4 Goals

Having a goal is important for every business. The method of goal setting used for Daoxiangcun brand is “Let the taste of China “. With this slogan Daoxiangcun brand aiming to open more branches in multiple cities in all over the China. Although, Daoxiangcun’s products are good, more people should know about it, especially the Southwest market with huge potential. During the Mid-Autumn Festival this year, Daoxiangcun brand will use Chengdu and Chongqing as its bridgeheads to increase publicity efforts to radiate Yunnan, Guizhou, Sichuan, Yunnan, Tibet and other vast areas. Focus on urban landmark sites with huge traffic such as Chunxi Road, South Railway Station, East Railway Station in Chengdu, Chongqing Guanyin Bridge, Lianglukou, Xiaoshizi and other important transfer points, and many subway line sites in the two cities of Chongqing and Chengdu Advertisements for food in Daoxiangcun brand can be seen everywhere.

4.3 Create media Account

The most important part of any company or brand to promote their company to choose the right new or any media official accounts for Advertising. Without the good new media account, this method of advertising can be very costly and low in profit. Therefore, the items put for sale on the new media site must be viral and sell good. This can be done by various ways depending on the target audience. As the focus of the new media for Advertising is Douyin so most of the items are taken from the trending and viral items on Douyin. That is one of the main sources of the most items of Daoxiangcun brand. The second method is finding out the best-selling items on a similar new media site like WeChat. It can be done by searching for similar items on Douyin. The bestselling items from a competitor’s new media site can then be outsourced and offered for a cheaper price. Once a viral item has been selected, it is

then outsourced on a Chinese website, in case of Douyin. AliExpress (www.aliexpress.com) is a leading global e-marketplace that is made up of many companies and brand that offer a huge variety of consumer products that have good value for money. It is dedicated to bringing products in more than 20 categories to its millions of registered users in more than 220 countries and regions (Y.Zhang & Y.Zhou, 2015).

4.3.1 Using AliExpress Search Engine

The method for finding brand or company Account site and products on AliExpress is using the search option. For using this method, the user needs to write the brand or products name, they want to search. The below figure shows the home screen of AliExpress mobile App. The small sign on the top right is the one used for search.

Figure11: How to search on AliExpress

Source: AliExpress Mobile App

4.3.2 WeChat search Engine

The method for finding brand or company Account site and products on WeChat is same as AliExpress App just user need to go on WeChat search engine option and write the brand name
Just Like this

Figure12: How to search on WeChat

Source: WeChat mobile App

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Planning Advertising Strategy

Advertising strategy with a creative plan for a successful advertising campaign is necessary for effective marketing. Without having one, it is as if you are going skydiving without first understanding how it works. The conversation you have with your audience plays a massive role in how successful your product or service will be. Although it gets challenging to launch an advertising strategy without backing it up with a creative plan in today's hectic world, having one helps you in the long term. So,

let's understand the benefits a creative plan can provide you when combined with an advertising strategy. Everything related to marketing should start with a careful planning of a advertising campaign. A ad campaign has to have a well-defined objective. Especially, if new media is going to be used for the campaigns, the brand need to further plan who they want to reach out to and what kind of new media strategy they are going to execute. During the execution process that brand needs to be ready to adjust the strategy according to the responses. Advise the brand to choose new media platforms based on the target group and the message that they want to convey. Also points out that, choosing an existing new media application has many benefits because of the existing user base. The reason why this can be a hard task is the fact that the landscape of new media is constantly changing. The new media networks that were popular a few years ago are not popular anymore and similarly many new social media networks have emerged in the past few years. All these rapid changes in the industry puts a high pressure on brand to keep their advertising strategies up to date and bring on changes with the changing landscape. In order to create the right ad campaign and stay up to date on new media.

5.2 Seasonal Advertising

China has a long history; China has many unique traditional festivals that other countries don't have. because Chinese people have special corresponding feeling for different Chinese traditional festivals, Daoxiangcun can launch so many series of "festival-limited" products based on the mental needs of consumers and the characteristics of those special Chinese festival customs.

Figure13: Limited products advertising

Source: sunlit Asian super mart

The seasonal products effectively and continuously increase Daoxiangcun brand influence in the China. For example, Daoxiangcun started launching short commercials video on the new media before the Mid- Autumn Festival. The advertising slogans focused on "train tickets", "Spring Festival Gala", "Reunion", and "Red Envelopes" and other Spring Festival elements that are associated with Chinese characteristics. Those keywords effectively capture the Local people's desire for family reunion before the Spring Festival. As traditional festivals, such as the Mid-Autumn Festival, are unique to China, Daoxiangcun brand try to seized the Chinese people's mood for the Mid-Autumn Festival reunion and made relevant advertisements, which aroused emotional resonance and promote the consumer's consumption on the relative products.

5.3 Influence of Advertising posters

Whenever people see and click on the Daoxiangcun official website, or walk into the daoxiangcun store ordering table to order food, they can see their promotions or new product posters, with the title usually "the second one is 10% off" "Moon cake golden gift box for a limited time of yuan ¥399

Figure 14: Promotional advertising poster

Source: Amazon.com

Daoxiangcun brand uses a lot of bright colors and puts colors with great contrast together, and the striking color contrasts cause a huge visual impact. What is more, it allows customers to notice new products at first sight after entering the store. At the same time, Daoxiangcun will enlarge the pictures, names, new product icons, and prices in the posters, which attract consumers' attention. Daoxiangcun brand takes the method of amplifying the visual effect, to make their consumers quickly obtain key information thereby promoting the dissemination and sale of their products.

5.4 Douyin Advertising Metric

There are a few basic advertising metrics that Daoxiangcun brand used to measure the effectiveness of Douyin ads. These metrics include ad views, ad clicks, and ad completion rates. Ad views refer to the number of times an ad is seen by users, while ad clicks refer to the number of times an ad is clicked on by users. Ad completion rates refer to the percentage of users who view an ad and then take the desired action, such as clicking on a link or purchasing a product. These metrics give valuable information for evaluating the ad campaign. Although these metrics are very useful, it should not be used as a final

resource for deciding the performance of a campaign rather more weightage should be given to the conversion and return on investment.

5.5 Douyin Advertising strategy

After carefully going through every step of the advertising strategy, it is time to make the Douyin advertising strategy. For effectively launching a advertising campaign, it is necessary to have a strategy. The strategy varies depending upon the type of business, as every business is unique. This chapter will deal with the findings and discussions about Douyin advertising.

5.6 Douyin Advertising Plan

In This part we will deal with the preparation, launch, evaluation and other details about how Daoxiangcun brand use Douyin advertising. The advertising plan consists of the following points:

1. The Daoxiangcun brand allocates an investment of \$100 for the advertising campaign.
2. The length of the campaign is one week
3. The two buying personas mentioned in chapter 4.5 are used.
4. The interests and professions for targeting are taken from Douyin Analytics data.
5. The main goals are: acquire Brand awareness, increase conversions and increase sales.
6. The final evaluation is based on total profit made and the return on investment.

5.7 Ad Format

Currently Douyin offers four ad formats, namely: Influencer Marketing, Brand takeover, In-feed ads. All of these formats have been discussed below.

5.7.1 Influencer Advertising

This is maybe the most important and effective method in the Chinese new media world. Consumers trust their peers, who feature their products, more than official accounts from brands. Plus, Chinese youth simply love social media. TikTok and Douyin superstars can create entertaining and engaging content, for example, a hashtag challenge, for your brand too! Create corporations that authentically boost your brand and turn your fans and followers into loyal customers.

Figure13: How influencer work

Source: Douyin mobile app

5.7.2 Brand Takeover

This ad will appear immediately when a user opens Douyin. It is usually a 3-5-second video of pictures or GIFs, or regular video content. Users tap the screen and arrive at a landing page, which is opened in the web view. This can be either an internal or external link, another video on TikTok, an external website, or an app. At the moment, this ad type is limited to one advertiser per day.

5.7.3 In-feed ads

The newsfeed in the Douyin app is basically a scrolling adventure that never ends. Videos play automatically when you scroll past them, this makes it so addictive, as users are simply drawn to video after video without pause. The in-feed native ad promotions are part of the organic newsfeed. The

TikTok/Douyin ads appear after the fourth refresh and can be an image or a 15-60 second video. It can include a message and an external link to your landing page, website, or app.

Conclusion

New media is becoming an undivided part of our everyday life. In modern world People are spending tens of hours every week on new media, either through their smartphones or computers. This thing has led many brands or companies to spend a significant amount of money on doing new media advertising. But without a proper strategy and understanding, these advertising campaigns do not bring any success. Making any advertising campaign is understanding the target audience. For targeting the right customers, a strong and targeted advertising plan is inevitable. The second step involves creating the advertising strategy. It involves a careful analysis of the brand. This analysis includes finding the interest and demographics of the current customers. Because without knowing these traits of current customers, the brand cannot find the potential customers. Setting goals is also an important part of the strategy. These goals have to be specific, measurable, attainable, relevant and time- bound. All these points are very important to remember while creating a advertising campaign.

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